

Measure the effectiveness of information systems with the naïve bayes classifier method

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ABSTRACT

Technological advances at this time are developing very fast, information systems became the frontline in technological advancements, the need for information systems to support jobs is increasingly high. However, its implementation for users does not have a significant impact, so that it needs to be reviewed and re-evaluated in the use of the information system built. The naïve bayes classifier method can provide "effective" and "ineffective" conclusions and is used as material for evaluation and improvement. The purpose of this study is to contribute to measuring the effectiveness of the information system, to solve problems with the naïve bayes classifier method approach which has advantages in the process of classifying data and predicting data. From the test results three times, training has been conducted using 100 data, accuracy value of 84.82% and error 15.18%.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information technology affects the progress of a company in optimizing performance by creating various information systems [1], [2]. Information system aims to improve service quality to the efficiency of work processes starting from presenting information to support operational functions to management functions [3]. Changes in the process of completing work from a manual system to a modern system where all activities carried out based on electronics known as e-office certainly have many disadvantages in its application. Therefore, an evaluation is needed to measure the effectiveness of information systems in a company. It can be measured using a decision support system [4], [5].

Decision support systems are defined as a system to support the management levels of an organization to make decisions in situations of semi-structured problems [6], [7]. This system is not intended to automate decision making but provides interactive tools that support decision making processes [8], [9]. Naïve bayes is an appropriate method used to measure the effectiveness of information systems, and this method is popularly used in classification techniques [10]. In the research, naïve bayes develops very similarly to the multinomial naïve bayes tree method, where one of the data mining techniques for the classification of raw data from customers [11], [12]. The results showed that the multinomial naïve bayes tree (MNBTree) approach had an accuracy rate of 16.26% with 145 features, while the accuracy rate with all 1665 feature datasets was 73.15% [13], [14].

In a previous study, produce a decision support system application with an accuracy level of 81.18% [15]. Therefore, this method was chosen because it was considered simple but produced accurate results [16]. In other studies discuss the sentiment analysis that has been raised in recent scientific studies. The method used is lexicon based and hybrid which is a combination of lexicon based techniques and machine learning. In this study, using the hadoop software framework using the naive bayes and naive bayes complement algorithms methods. Experiments conducted with 8 million reviews were classified as positive, negative and neutral and used various training dataset sizes and around. The performance of the algorithm is measured according to the criteria of precision, accuracy, size-F and calls [17], [18].

In other research on the effectiveness of information systems, the calculation model and evaluation of system effectiveness are based on the analytic hierarchy process (AHP), where the system architecture can be evaluated to support the characteristics of the dataset. [19], [20]. The purpose of this study is to develop a decision support system to analyze the effectiveness of the implementation of information systems using a web-based naïve bayes classifier that can help companies to evaluate and determine the appropriate follow-up. This study uses 8 assessment attributes which consist of ease of use of the system, benefits of the system, speed of completion of work, improvement of work effectiveness, the information generated, speed of information presentation, improvement of service quality, the suitability of the system with needs, and 1 attribute conclusion namely conclusions. From these attributes predictions will be generated in the form of conclusions about the effectiveness of information systems based on previous assessment data.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The stages of research that will be carried out in making a decision support system to assess information systems using the naïve bayes classifier method are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Phase of research

2.1. System requirements analysis

1. Data

The data needed is questionnaire data about the information system that has been filled by the user.

2. Hardware
3. Software

The software used for the design of the system include:

- a. XAMPP version 3.2.2
- b. Notepad++

2.2. Data collection

Data collected in the form of primary data that is a data-assessment questionnaire obtained directly from the data source. Besides, used some literature that was secondary data.

2.2.1. Primary data

Primary data is taken in the form of 100 questionnaire data consisting of 8 assessment criteria written as K1 to K8. Each criterion has 4 members, namely value. Each value has a level from strongly agree (4) to strongly disagree (1). The results of the assessment produce conclusions consisting of effective and Ineffective. Effective results are obtained based on the average rating of 3.00-4.00. Effective results are based on an average rating of <3.00. Effective results are based on an average rating of <3.00. 3 samples of 100 primary data taken are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample of primary data

Name	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	Conclusion
Sangapan	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	Effective
Ratna Kusuma	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	3	Effective
Name	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	Conclusion
Suri Mulyani	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	Ineffective

2.2.2. Secondary data

Literature studies are carried out by studying problems related to the object under study, and getting appropriate references in applying a method, for example by studying several books, journals, and articles related to the problem under study.

2.3. Naïve bayes classifier

Naïve bayes is a classification method based on teorama bayes [21]. The naïve bayes algorithm, which assumes that each variable is independent, independent from each other, has no relationship or correlation that can affect the results [22]. Predictions based on the bayes theorem general formula in (1) [23]:

$$P(H|X) = \frac{P(X|H)P(H)}{P(X)} \quad (1)$$

Once the data is collected, carried out the data processing through data cleansing, data integration, data selection, data transformation [24], and the establishment of the dataset that will be used as training data and testing data [25], [26].

2.4. Analysis of results and conclusions

The final stage is to analyze the accuracy of the results in assessing the effectiveness of the information system, hereinafter referred to as the conclusion.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Data preparation

At this stage, 100 questionnaires were used as training data. Known class of "Effective" as much as 95 data and class "Not Effective" by 5 data. The data consists of eight attributes and one attribute ranking member and the probabilities are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Table frequencies (*continue*)

No.	Attribute	Member	Frequency
1.	Ease of use of the system	Very easy to use	60
		Easy to use	39
		Difficult to use	1
		Very difficult to use	0
2.	Benefits of the system	Strongly agree	72
		Agree	28
		Disagree	0
		Strongly disagree	0
3.	Speed of completion of work	Very fast	42
		Fast	55
		Not fast	3
		Very fast	0
4.	Increasing the effectiveness of the work	Very true	46
		Right	51
		Not true	3
		Very true	0
5.	Information generated	Strongly agree	57
		Agree	40
		Disagree	2
		Strongly disagree	0
6.	Speed of presenting information	Strongly agree	41
		Agree	57
		Disagree	2
		Strongly disagree	0

Table 2. Table frequencies

No.	Attribute	Member	Frequency
7.	Improved quality of service	Strongly agree	62
		Agree	38
		Disagree	0
		Strongly disagree	0
		Very appropriate	42
8.	The suitability of the system to the needs of	Corresponding	56
		It is not in accordance with	2
		Very appropriate	0
9.	Conclusion	Effective	95
		Ineffective	5

3.2. System testing

System testing is done in two ways, namely by looking at the accuracy of the system and comparing the calculations produced by the system with manual calculations.

1. Test the accuracy of the system

System accuracy testing is done to find out how the naïve bayes classifier method works to provide accuracy and error values [17]. The test was conducted three times on 100 training data with different testing data.

The first test with 100 training data and 25 testing data.

accuracy value = $(21/25) * 100\% = 84\%$

Error value = $(4/25) * 100\% = 16\%$

The second test with 100 training data and 40 testing data.

accuracy value = $(34/40) * 100\% = 85\%$

Error value = $(6/40) * 100\% = 15\%$

The third test with 100 training data and 55 testing data.

accuracy value = $(47/55) * 100\% = 85.45\%$

Error value = $(8/55) * 100\% = 14.55\%$

2. Manual calculations

The second test is done by comparing the results of the system calculation with the results of manual calculations shown in Figure 2.

No	Nama	K 1	K 2	K 3	K 4	K 5	K 6	K 7	K 8
1	Admin	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	4
2	Dinda Audilla	2	2	3	2	1	2	3	2
3	Dita Pramesti	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	4
4	Elis Muhlishoh	4	4	3	3	3	3	4	3

Figure 2. Examples of data test

The stages of testing the manual calculation sample data in Table 3, which are obtained from the primary data sample, are carried out by:

a. Defining variables

Table 3. Definition of variables

X	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3	Value 4
K1	4	2	4	4
K2	4	2	3	4
K3	3	3	4	3
K4	3	2	3	3
K5	3	1	4	3
K6	3	2	3	3
K7	3	3	4	4
K8	4	2	4	3

b. Defining the prior probability

Prior probability that consists of classes effective (H1) and ineffective (H0) based on Table 2 are defined as (2) and (3):

$$P(H1) / P(X) = 95/100 = 0.95 \tag{2}$$

$$P(H0) / P(X) = 5/100 = 0.05 \tag{3}$$

c. The posterior probability calculation

The criteria for calculating the probability (X) per class (H) in Table 4.

Table 4. Posterior probability

		Value 1		Value 2		Value 3		Value 4	
		H ₁	H ₀						
POSTERIOR PROBABILITIES	K1	0.6315	0	0.0000	0.2	0.6316	0	0.6316	0
	K2	0.7578	0	0.0000	0.2	0.3684	0.8	0.6316	0
	K3	0.5473	0.6	0.3684	0.8	0.6316	0	0.3684	0.8
	K4	0.5157	0.4	0.0000	0.2	0.3684	0.8	0.3684	0.8
	K5	0.3789	0.8	0.0000	0	0.6316	0	0.3684	0.8
	K6	0.5684	0.6	0.0000	0.2	0.3684	0.8	0.3684	0.8
	K7	0.3473	1	0.3684	0.8	0.6316	0	0.6316	0
	K8	0.4421	0	0.0000	0.2	0.6316	0	0.3684	0.8

d. Final probability calculation

The final calculated probability by multiplying the previous probability by the posterior probability of each class shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Final probability

	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3	Value 4
P (X H ₁)	0.004466368	0	0.00502541	0.001710036
P (H ₁) / P (X)	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95
P (H ₁ X)	0.00424305	0	0.00477414	0.001624534
P (X H ₀)	0	0	0	0
P (H ₀) / P (X)	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
P (H ₀ X)	0	0	0	0

From the calculations in Table 6, the P-value (H1 | X) will be compared with P (H0 | X). If the value of P (H1 | X) > P (H0 | X), it can be concluded that the data entered is classified into the Effective class. However, if the value of P (H1 | X) < P (H0 | X), it can be concluded that the data entered is classified into Ineffective classes. The results of comparison of the four assessment samples that have been included as shown in Table 6. This result will be compared with the system prediction results as shown in Table 7. The system prediction results in Table 6 show that the conclusions from the prediction results are the same as manual calculations.

Table 6. Comparison of the calculation results

	Comparison	Conclusion
Value 1	P (H ₁ X) > P (H ₀ X)	EFFECTIVE
Value 2	P (H ₁ X) < P (H ₀ X)	INEFFECTIVE
Value 3	P (H ₁ X) > P (H ₀ X)	EFFECTIVE
Value 4	P (H ₁ X) > P (H ₀ X)	EFFECTIVE

Table 7. System calculation results

No	Name	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	Conclusion
1	Budi	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	EFFECTIVE
2	Andi	2	2	3	2	1	2	3	2	INEFFECTIVE
3	Rita	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	EFFECTIVE
4	Dinda	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	EFFECTIVE

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the system accuracy test conducted three times using 100 training data resulted in an accuracy value of 84% for 25 test data, 85% for 40 test data, and a maximum value of 85.45% for 55 test data. With a relatively stable value of accuracy and error values and the results of system calculations with relatively similar manual calculations, the decision support system is right to be applied to the naïve bayes classifier method approach to assess the effectiveness of information systems with an average accuracy value of 84.82%.

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